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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Sharq mutafakkirlari, xususan, Abu Nasr Forobiy, Yusuf Xos Hojib, Nizomulmulk, Amir Temur va Alisher Navoiy ta'limotlari davlat fuqarolik xizmatchilarining siyosiy madaniyatini shakllantirishda axloq, adolat, bilim va xalqqa xizmat qilish kabi qadriyatlarning muhimligini ko'rsatadi. Ularning g'oyalari zamonaviy davlat xizmatida odoq-axloq kodekslarini ishlab chiqish, malaka oshirish tizimlarini rivojlantirish va fuqarolik jamiyati bilan ishonchli munosabatlarni o'rnatishda muhim manba bo'lib xizmat qiladi. O'zbekistonning milliy-ma'naviy merosi bilan uyg'unlashgan bu ta'limotlar davlat boshqaruvini yanada samarali va adolatli qilishga xizmat qilmoqda. Shuningdek, mutafakkirlarning g'oyalari kadrlar siyosatiga oid qonunchilikni takomillashtirishda metodologik manba bo'lishi mumkinligini haqida fikr mulohazalar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Davlat xizmati, davlat fuqarolik xizmati, siyosiy madaniyat, siyosiy fazilatlar, baxt-saodat, bilag'on, sezgir, farovon jamiyat.

THEORETICAL ANALYSIS OF THE TEACHINGS OF ORIENTAL THINKERS ON THE POLITICAL CULTURE OF STATE CIVIL SERVANTS

Abstract: The article highlights that the teachings of Eastern thinkers, particularly Abu Nasr Farabi, Yusuf Khos Hojib, Nizamulmulk, Amir Temur, and Alisher Navoi, emphasize the importance of values such as morality, justice, knowledge, and service to the people in shaping the political culture of civil servants. Their ideas serve as a vital resource for developing ethical codes, advancing professional development systems, and fostering trust-based relationships with civil society in modern public service. Aligned with Uzbekistan's national and spiritual heritage, these teachings contribute to making state governance more effective and just. Additionally, the article suggests that the ideas of these thinkers can serve as a methodological foundation for improving legislation related to personnel policy.

Key words: Public service, civil service, political culture, political virtues, happiness and well-being, knowledgeable, sensitive, prosperous society.

INTRODUCTION

The political culture of civil servants is of great importance in the effectiveness of state administration and the construction of a just society. Eastern thinkers, in particular, Central Asian scholars, have paid special attention to the moral and political qualities of civil servants, the principles of responsibility and justice. Below is a theoretical analysis of the political culture of civil servants based on the teachings of such thinkers as Abu Nasr Al-Farabi, Yusuf Khos Hajib, Nizamulmulk, Amir Temur and Alisher Navoi.

Indeed, unlike Western individualism, “in Central Asia, the sense of community is of paramount importance... If we look at the way of life and thinking of our people, we see a number of unique features that are unique to no one else, formed over thousands of years, manifested not only in mutual interaction, but also as an integral part of our lives... When talking about such distinctive features of the peoples of the East and the people of our country, special attention should be paid to their historical and social background”[1]. “Considering that the state and public administration in the territories of the Republic of Uzbekistan were formed in the middle of the third millennium BC,”[2] “it becomes clear that our people have a very rich history and experience in the issues of public service, management culture and activity”[3].

Literature analysis and methodology. Some theoretical and practical problems related to this topic have also been studied by our country's scientists, and we found it necessary to separate this aspect into the following groups, including: 1) from legal scholars F.Muhitdinova, Sh.I.Jalilov, S.Sultonov, A.Saidov, M.Suvonkulov, A.Tulaganov, G.Malikova, G.Ismailova; 2) from a historical point of view R.Murtazayeva, G.Umarova, R.Shamsutdinov, A.Ishokov, V.Ishkuvatov, F.Tolipov; 3) from a political point of view, we can see that the teachings, views, approaches and concepts of scientists such as M. Kyrgyzbayev, Q. Qurbanbayev, Sh. Minovarov, M. Quronov, G. Marufova, 4) from a sociological point of view, such as M. Bekmurodov, Sh. Sodiqova and Kh. Khusanova, on improving the political culture of civil servants, have been studied.

Discussion and results. In particular, in this regard, “the work “City of Virtuous People” by Abu Nasr al-Farabi (873-950) is of incomparable importance. The work systematically expresses the training, selection and requirements for civil servants”[4].

It should also be noted that al-Farabi's views on the culture of management reflect many of the views expressed on the issues of state and society management, the leaders who manage them, officials and officials.

In his works, he analyzes these issues as a whole. Speaking about society, he also expresses his thoughts on the personal and professional character of its governing officials, their characteristics of action. In this regard, according to al-Farabi, “It can be said that all types and any organizations, all officials, leaders and their activities are a single phenomenon, the foundations of which are connected with the foundations of the development of the state and society”[5].

According to Abu Nasr Al-Farabi, “the purpose of a person's coming to this world and living is to achieve happiness. The key to the doors of happiness is in the hands of the person himself. People achieve this goal by becoming the owners of virtuous deeds and good moral qualities. Therefore, happiness and the means of achieving it - virtuous deeds - are inextricably linked, and happiness is not an abstract concept (moral or social ideal) that a person dreams of, but is the product of the active actions and results of virtuous deeds of all members of the community. Here we are not talking about the personal happiness of each person, but rather the well-being, happiness, and the manifestation of noble intentions of the members of an entire community. Such happiness (social ideal) can be achieved only in a virtuous society. A virtuous society (Al-Farabi calls it a virtuous city, or a virtuous

community) The difference between the lifestyle and activities of the people of the city and the lives of people in other imperfect societies is that if a group of (virtuous) people together possess these qualities (virtues) (i.e., one has this, the other has that, and the third has another (beautiful) quality), then this group of virtues should exercise control. If the members of this group come together and act in agreement with each other, society can achieve the goals it seeks from the system of governance. The city of virtues, its inhabitants, need to know what happiness their hearts can achieve. Also... the inhabitants of the city of virtues need to know what they will achieve in the afterlife and what to avoid"[6].

In our opinion, the significant aspect of this work is that it is far from utopian (imaginary) views, and is based on empirical research and practical life.

Another thinker, Yusuf Khos Hajib (11th century), in his work "Kutadgu Bilig" ("Knowledge Leading to Happiness"), offers the most fair criteria for selecting civil servants, in particular, leaders, using the example of figurative heroes. "Speaking about the requirements for civil servants, Yusuf Khos Hajib puts forward the following wise thoughts: "The behavior of a minister should be pleasing to the majority, and his tongue and heart should be one. Those who have a shameless mind and a clean heart are worthy of this position. Those who are sharp-eyed, intelligent, sensitive, and who distinguish between good and evil are worthy of the ministry"[7].

All the issues expressed in the work are distinguished by their focus on the criteria, procedures, manners and characteristics of the field of management culture, civil service and civil servants. In particular, according to the views of Khos Hajib, Allah made man a caliph on earth and ordered him to multiply. As a result, a human society was formed, living in a whirlpool of many needs. All of them have justice, need, property, knowledge and patience. But they are at different levels, high and low. In order to resolve these levels in an orderly manner, Allah made one of them responsible for managing this society. The person in charge (meaning the management system, leaders) is responsible for determining the position of people in society depending on their level. If a society has a management system and leaders consisting of people belonging to the upper category of these levels, it will certainly be a noble, developing and prosperous society. For this, the management system and leadership are required to be faithful to their responsibility - justice. In a word, if people live in justice, are content with their status, and this prosperity leads to development, then this political system, public service is noble and good. This system - the state will live long. If there are many disputes over justice, and citizens live in confusion, unrest, and fear, then this system is evil and bad. Soon the citizens will also become evil and forget their status, and eventually they will destroy this state. Accordingly, the civil service and its employee must first of all know the criteria that determine the status of people.

Another important source on public service is the work of Nizam al-Mulk (11th century) "Siyosatnama" - "Siyar ul-Muluk" [8]. Nizam al-Mulk served as a minister in the Seljuk state (1038-1308). He was a minister with very good qualities. His personality was highly appreciated by statesmen and scholars. For example, Amir Temur respectfully mentions Nizam-ul-Mulk in several places in his "Temur Tuzuklari", including the following: "Malikshah Seljuqi demoted his minister Nizam-ul-Mulk. The minister was

surrounded by good qualities from head to toe. He appointed a low-born, bad person as minister in his place. At this step, the palace began to collapse due to the minister's evil deeds, oppression, and depravity" [9]. In addition to the rules of Sharia, the work "Siyosatnama" recommends rules of governance for state officials based on the characteristics of a secular state. These rules of governance can even be recognized as "arts of governance." In particular, Nizamulmulk, speaking about staffing the civil service, emphasizes that "selecting officials correctly, assigning them the work and tasks they can handle, giving one person a task and expecting obedience and execution from him is one of the main requirements of state administration. It is envisaged that officials will act in consultation in every matter"[10].

The views of the great statesman Amir Temur on the state civil service are set out in the "Temur Statutes", and some of the qualities of state civil servants highlighted in them are still relevant today. Amir Temur governed the country, adhering to the motto "Strength is in justice." "Sahibkiran, in addition to following this motto himself, also encouraged state officials to follow it. It can be said that other qualities assigned to ministers and civil servants were formed precisely from this motto. Amir Temur considered "the ruler's ability to select officials and place them in their places to be the main condition for exercising and strengthening power"[11]. The scholar of Temur, academician B. Ahmedov emphasizes that "Amir Temur created a compact system of governance: as for the central state system, it was headed by only seven ministers: 1) the minister of the country and the people, 2) the minister of the army, 3) the minister of finance, 4) the minister of the affairs of the kingdom; The fifth, sixth, seventh ministers - border ministers - ruled. [12]

In our opinion, the perfection of the state administration established by Sahibkiran Amir Temur and its adherence to the principles of justice, the fact that each decision of the ruler was made by consulting with the umars and scholars, the benefit-harm, difficulty-ease, good-bad, danger-safety of the work, the provision of unanimity in opinions, vigilance, caution, and the unconditional implementation of the ruler's decisions show that the rules accumulated in those times on the basis of millennia of experience and traditions, embodied in the theoretical views on governance in states that left a name for themselves in history with their power, indicate that the civil service system in the Turanian state was formed in a unique manner. In addition, Amir Temur also based on his own experiences in building a large and centralized state and perfect theoretical rules, principles, procedures, and practices for the management of society were created.

"Amir Temur, in his regulations, setting out the main principles and criteria of civil service, notes that it is based on the following fundamental principles: justice; compliance with regulations; consultation and deliberation; firm decision-making, entrepreneurship, vigilance and caution; patience; courage and zeal"[13]. In addition to adopting these values of state administration as principles for his own ruling activities, Amir Temur also requires officials at all levels under his authority to strictly adhere to them.

The great thinker Alisher Navoi lived a fruitful life as both a poet and writer and a statesman, and his views included the issues of a perfect person, in particular, an accomplished civil servant and a public servant. His reflections on this matter were

expressed in the works “Saddi Iskandariy” and “Mahbub ul-qulub” (“The Beloved of the Hearts”)[14].

Thus, the records of Alisher Navoi that have come down to us through historical sources show that he was not only a great poet, but also a brilliant statesman, a person of great potential, energy and enthusiasm, a wise leader with great influence, a wise leader. Undoubtedly, he made a great contribution to the rise of the Khorasan state in his time, and this contribution was made not only by fulfilling tasks, but also by taking the initiative, organizing, providing and controlling. According to these aspects, Alisher Navoi is also among the great statesmen.

Researching the political and legal teachings of Eastern thinkers, the lawyer F. Muhitdinova emphasizes that “the ideas in them regarding personnel policy are of great importance in the training and improvement of the qualifications of state power and administration employees, including managerial personnel”[15]. In addition to these thoughts, it is worth noting that the ideas of the above thinkers can be a methodological resource for improving legislation on personnel policy.

In conclusion, the teachings of Eastern thinkers serve as an important theoretical basis for the formation of the political culture of civil servants. Thinkers such as Abu Nasr Farobi, Yusuf Khos Hajib, Nizamulmulk, Amir Temur, Alisher Navoi, emphasizing the principles of justice, morality, professionalism, and service to the people, taught the need for civil servants to have a high political culture. The reforms being implemented in Uzbekistan, in particular, measures aimed at transparency, combating corruption, and improving the quality of service, are consistent with these teachings.

The application of these teachings in modern conditions serves to strengthen the political culture of civil servants, increase citizen trust, and enhance the effectiveness of public administration. At the same time, the full implementation of these ideas requires taking into account cultural and institutional factors and their integration with modern management methods.

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